

Arbitrary Variations and the Almost Homogenous Universe – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the 8T framework, it becomes vividly clear that the universe or the Lorentzian manifold can't not be completely homogenous. Our framework contains arbitrary variations, proved to vanish into matter. Therefore, the structure of the universe and large fermion clusters are validating the framework of the 8 theory. A reasoning for the fast formation of the galaxies can be made by using the coupling constant equation and the elements, which were neglected to this day after the coupling of electromagnetism.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g'}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The reason the universe is not completely homogenous based on the framework is that the manifold Experience arbitrary variations – which than vanish into fermions. Marked in green.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Those variations are arbitrary amount of curvature of a manifold, and they are subject to net variations, which yielded the coupling constant equation. We saw that nature is really the interplay between total arbitrary variations to net variations. Net variations are prime in their nature, and so in the 8- theory Framework for each prime number there exist a boson.

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

The series gives rise to the arrow of time; we should see more interactions as time goes on and so, bigger and bigger structures which makes the manifold less and less homogenous. The bigger the Cluster of total variations the weaker the force, as it is divided across the whole cluster. By looking at those two equations we can see exactly why the universe or the Lorentz manifold in The 8-theory framework is not homogenous, because of those arbitrary variations and the additional Net variations. The first accounts for fermions, known as quarks, the other known as bosons.

Using that framework, we can see why the manifold cannot be homogenous, it is almost obvious. Of course, the question of the homogenous structure is a question in which we cannot really Answer, as it has no numerical data, it's a question revolving around a theory in which the lack of Homogeny is a feature of the main axioms and equations. We can see it in the framework of the 8-theory, or any Lagrangian oriented theory, which includes arbitrary variations, which must vanish at border. The beauty and innovative part in the 8-theory is that, all life forms, galaxies, clusters of galaxies **are** those arbitrary variations. The fast formation of galaxies can be solved by adding all the terms which no one knew existed after the coupling of the electric. Those are immensely stronger than the gravitational coupling, and so must be taken into account in fermionic mega scale formations.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)